

Monitoring and Evaluating Policy Reforms in the EU¹

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Policy Recommendations

1. **Provide ready-to-use comprehensive monitoring mechanisms:** The Technical Support Instrument (TSI) could provide the member states with an enhanced monitoring mechanism that includes scoreboards and common indicators that measure outcomes and impacts, not just outputs.
2. **Obligatory Impact Assessments:** Make technical support from TSI contingent upon member states submitting independent impact assessments and follow-up assessments within specified timeframes.
3. **Promoting Best Practices:** Identify and promote lessons from successful monitoring experiences and best practices across member states. Facilitating knowledge exchange can contribute to the development of more effective monitoring frameworks.
4. Strengthen the **culture** of monitoring and evaluating policy with **awareness campaigns, seminars, training**, and other activities.

Introduction

In this policy brief, we provide a set of **4 policy recommendations** for improving the **monitoring framework** of EU member states within the context of the work of the **Technical Support Instrument (TSI)** of **DG REFORM**. The Technical Support Instrument (TSI) is a critical component of the European Union's technical support framework, designed to provide member states with essential technical support. This support aims

to enhance **institutional and administrative capacities** for designing and implementing reforms.

Policy reforms in the EU may be triggered by national priorities or by the need to comply with EU priorities stemming from EU legal framework. What is crucial is to develop effective political strategies for reform and **incentivise** the engagement and **political commitment** of national governments, but as importantly of national administrative units,

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which usually transcend multiple election cycles.

Especially within the context of Next Generation EU instrument and the Recovery and Resilience Facility plans of member states, monitoring reforms is important, to guarantee that EU taxpayers' money has an impact on strengthening EU economies and societies and making them robust and futureproof. Consequently, **incentivizing member states to monitor policy reforms** requires careful examination of the theoretical and empirical findings of the literature as well as the critical study of the monitoring systems applied in international governmental organizations.

In the following section we critically review the academic literature and briefly outline the theoretical background behind monitoring systems of policy reforms, whereas in the third section, we present the current challenges to the TSI framework and monitoring schemes. The fourth section outlines best practices, and the last section presents our policy recommendations.

Theoretical Background

The introduction of **performance incentives** has a historical foundation in project management, particularly evident in the US Department of Defense contracts during WWI and WWII. Meng (2015) highlights the success of extending these incentives during the 1960s to NASA, ensuring the accomplishment of large, complex projects like the Apollo program. Studies have consistently demonstrated the positive application of incentives in diverse construction and engineering projects across different countries (Doloi et al., 2012; Floricel & Miller, 2001; Meng, 2015). This holds also for policymaking initiatives such political and

structural reforms (Banerji et al., 2015; Di Mascio et al., 2020; Schimmelfennig & Sedelmeier, 2004).

1. A crucial aspect of the incentives literature on **policy reforms monitoring** is the emphasis it places on the transition from **output-based** to **outcome-based** measurement systems in the public sector. The shift towards outcome-based measures gained prominence with the Clinton Administration and the Government Performance and Results Act of 1993, mandating outcomes-based performance evaluation for federal government programs (Rajala et al., 2018). The World Bank's recent prioritization of shifting incentives from inputs to outcomes further underscores the global trend towards outcome-oriented evaluation (Echebarria, 2023). **Information** about outcomes is a relevant issue in the literature and policy-making community of the public sector. It is important because outcome-information reports whether a service is creating the desired results to society. However, designing and establishing an outcome-oriented measurement system is not always an easy task. There is a debate in the literature as to the merits of outputs-based versus outcomes-based performance systems, which is more cost-effective, which is better in expressing whether targets are met. A contentious issue in the literature is how to define outcomes and how to measure them (De Lancer Julnes, 2006; Rajala et al., 2018).
2. Dolls et al. (2019), however, offer a nuanced analysis of the potential adverse effects of **incentivizing governments** through fiscal transfers. They argue that the rationale for incentivizing structural reforms in EU Member States lies in

overcoming obstacles related to the **timing** and **distribution** of **costs** and **benefits**. While economic costs may be immediate, benefits may take time to materialize, leading to reform fatigue. Political challenges arise as gains may be dispersed, while losses, borne by a smaller group, attract more attention. They propose the concept of '**national convergence roadmaps**' as a countermeasure. These roadmaps involve member states **jointly agreeing on targets** and specifying **timelines** for achieving these goals. By committing themselves into jointly agreed targets and timelines, the member states gain more flexibility with respect to achieving goals that are in line with domestic policy preferences and politico-economic circumstances, as well as account for reform paths that generate positive spillovers. Furthermore, this collaborative approach enhances **national ownership** of structural reforms. In the context of reform evaluation within the Technical Support Instrument (TSI) framework, member states, through ex ante assessments, could present the potential of each reform in achieving specific goals. The European Commission and the Council would then review and assess these goals, potentially unlocking financial support in tranches upon achieving important milestones.

3. A third strategy is '**naming and shaming**'. Naming and shaming, as a social process, involves exposing **inappropriate behavior** either to the public or a group of peers. Apparently, it is effective in the enforcement of human rights agreements. As for performance improvements (De Witte & Saal, 2010); or specific education policies (Cabus & De Witte, 2012; De Witte & Van Klaveren,

2012), naming and shaming's application in education reform faces challenges due to the national competence of education policy within the EU. The literature explores whether naming and shaming "works" as a mechanism for cooperation enforcement and underlines the circumstances influencing its effectiveness (Carraro et al., 2019; Keck & Sikkink, 2014; Murdie & Urpelainen, 2015). It highlights the importance of emotional responses like **shame, guilt, or embarrassment** in generating social pressure and emphasizes the need for **political actors** to care about their **reputations** for this mechanism to be effective. Carraro et al. (2019) highlight **three institutional features**: specificity of recommendations; transparency of reviews to the public; and possibilities for follow-up monitoring. These facilitate the exertion of peer and public pressure.

Current Challenges of the TSI Framework

In 2020 an **independent mid-term report** was conducted by the consulting firm **Ernst & Young** (2020) finding important obstacles and challenges to be addressed in the current system of implementing, delivering, and monitoring policy reforms from member states. First, the mid-term report found that EU member states highly appreciate the TSI due to its high degree of flexibility, the simplicity of the contracting and implementing procedures and the absence of co-financing requirements.

However, the report highlights significant **obstacles** in the delivery of policy reforms outputs due to the potential changes in the political structure of EU member states governments **(1)** and the lack of collaboration

among national stakeholders **(2)**. Another challenge that was flagged by the consultation respondents was the limited administrative and institutional capacity of national authorities **(3)** (e.g., poorly staffed or equipped, weak organizations, institutional bottlenecks with overlaps of mandates, limited capacity to implement). Further, there was only a limited number of EU member states that had mechanisms in place to monitor the progress achieved at the project level **(4)** (e.g., the status of activities and results), whereas no member state had created any mechanism to monitor the effects of TSI participation.

Similar observations were made by the **European Court of Auditors** special report, this time for the monitoring framework of the Recovery and Resilience Facility. The special report emphasizes that the RRF monitoring system, including Member States' milestones and targets, predominantly focuses on outputs rather than results **(5)**, with limited consideration for impacts. Even when data on common indicators are gathered and reported, these are often based on estimates **(6)**. The report noted variations in ambition levels among Member States regarding milestones, particularly in training-related measures **(7)**. To enhance consistency, the ECA proposed homogenizing these targets through DG Reform. Additionally, the ECA provided recommendations for a comprehensive performance monitoring and evaluation framework, emphasizing a combination of milestones/targets and common indicators reflecting results and impacts.

Current Good Practices

International organizations like the OECD and the USAID have employed a diverse array of methodologies for monitoring policy reforms.

The OECD (2018), as part of its **Economic Reform Program (ERP)**, offers to countries and policymakers a monitoring tool, the **ERP Monitoring Tool**. One crucial element of the monitoring process that the OECD proposes is the **evaluation of the economic impact of the reforms**, which usually is not so straightforward to policymakers, politicians, or the public. As a solution to this problem the ERP Monitoring Tool offers a **variety of methodologies** and tools to evaluate the direct and indirect impacts of policy reforms and estimate the economic (or other) value-added. Among the methodologies that the OECD proposes to policymakers and governments are:

- the compilation of databases which measure **observable effects** to a particular sector of the economy and the conduct of surveys and other empirical measurements,
- the use of **input-output models** that capture the direct and indirect effects of a reform inter-sectorally,
- **econometric models** that estimate the impacts to the whole economy, including simulations and forecasting.

Promoting policy reforms is an important tool in USAID's overall development assistance kit, with monitoring being a key element of the agency's programs, keeping implementation on track and yielding insights on the effectiveness of the strategy deployed. According to the USAID (2000) the most important characteristics of a **good monitoring system** are: **a)** it is user-friendly for those who report the status of the policy reform; **b)** follows all the necessary steps of the reform; **c)** it is cost-effective; **d)** provides detailed descriptions of the stages of the reform and the methodology used to identify completion of each stage; **e)** defines clearly key terms in the implementation of the reform. One important challenge for policy

implementation is that for some policy reforms that are more complex in nature, the payoffs for carrying out such policies are usually remote and uncertain, affecting the political will of local authorities. USAID addresses this challenge by introducing **Policy Implementation Milestones**, whose role is to: **a)** develop ownership and support for the policy within the government and civil society through dialogue; **b)** develop a detailed policy implementation plan; **c)** achieve political compromises among conflicting stakeholder groups; **d)** allocate – if applicable – financial resources, among others.

Conclusions

Given all these considerations, how can the European Commission **nurture the logic of monitoring** the results of policy reforms to member states, when these reforms are not implemented by the EU but by the member state itself? In what follows we offer 4 policy recommendations:

1. **Provide ready-to-use comprehensive monitoring mechanisms:** The TSI could provide the member states with an enhanced monitoring mechanism that includes of scoreboards and common indicators that measure outcomes and impacts, not just outputs. This shift towards comprehensive monitoring ensures a more accurate assessment of policy effectiveness. Potential challenges arising from political changes such as the loss of interest or ownership for a particular reform by a newly elected government, are critical for the success of the process. However, simplifying the identification and monitoring of outcomes and impacts for member states, significantly increases the

likelihood of sustaining reforms even in the event of government changes. Outcome-based reforms are inherently easier to explain and appropriate politically. Focusing on outcomes and impacts provides a compelling political narrative that can transcend political transitions and incentivize succeeding governments to build upon established policies and exploit political value-added. The scoreboards and common indicators should be specifically designed for each policy area, such as taxation, education, health, digital transition, etc.

2. **Pre-Request Structured Questionnaire:** Before seeking TSI support, member states should respond to a structured questionnaire outlining the targets and aims of the proposed policy reform. This upfront assessment ensures a clear understanding of the reform's objectives and sets the stage for effective technical support. Given that member states are already required to submit a similar template, there is a need to monitor the effects of this practice.
3. **Obligatory Impact Assessments:** Make technical support from TSI contingent upon member states submitting independent impact assessments and follow-up assessments within specified timeframes. This ensures accountability and provides valuable insights into the long-term effects of implemented reforms.
4. **Promoting Best Practices:** Identify and promote lessons from successful

monitoring experiences and best practices across member states. Facilitating knowledge exchange can contribute to the development of more effective monitoring frameworks. This can be effectively achieved with the creation of an accessible online tool that shares best practices of member states. In that direction, integrating recommendations for monitoring reforms within the European Semester process can also enhance the effectiveness of the TSI. In that respect, “naming and shaming” practices that induce indirect peer pressure from other member states, should also be considered. It is essential to recognize that Naming and Shaming practices are specifically designed for cases where we lack legally binding obligations. The application of 'naming and shaming' becomes a pragmatic approach in situations where legal obligations are absent, as it serves as a mechanism to influence behavior and encourage compliance in the absence of direct enforcement measures.

5. Strengthen the **culture** of monitoring and evaluating policy with **awareness campaigns, seminars, training**, and other activities. Key stakeholders and government officials will increase their demand for monitor and evaluation systems if they become aware of cost-effective examples of other governments that have set-up such systems and begin to understand the potential benefits from their implementation. Likewise, providing relevant training, procedural blueprints and manuals, will educate member states government

administration and consequently enhance the culture of monitoring and evaluating policy reforms.

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

References

- Banerji, A., Barkbu, B., John, J., Kinda, T., Saksonovs, S., Schoelermann, H., & Wu, T. (2015). Building a Better Union: Incentivizing Structural Reforms in the Euro Area. *IMF Working Papers*, 15(201), 1. <https://doi.org/10.5089/9781513517087.001>
- Cabus, S. J., & De Witte, K. (2012). Naming and shaming in a 'fair' way. On disentangling the influence of policy in observed outcomes. *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 34(5), 767-787.
- Carraro, V., Conzelmann, T., & Jongen, H. (2019). Fears of peers? Explaining peer and public shaming in global governance. *Cooperation and Conflict*, 54(3), 335-355. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0010836718816729>
- De Lancer Julnes, P. (2006). Performance Measurement: An Effective Tool for Government Accountability? *The Debate Goes On. Evaluation*, 12(2), 219-235.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/135638900606669>
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- De Witte, K., & Saal, D. S. (2010). Is a little sunshine all we need? On the impact of sunshine regulation on profits, productivity and prices in the Dutch drinking water sector. *Journal of Regulatory Economics*, 37, 219-242.
- De Witte, K., & Van Klaveren, C. (2012). Comparing students by a matching analysis—on early school leaving in Dutch cities. *Applied Economics*, 44(28), 3679-3690.
- Di Mascio, F., Natalini, A., Ongaro, E., & Stolfi, F. (2020). Influence of the European Semester on national public sector reforms under conditions of fiscal consolidation: The policy of conditionality in Italy 2011-2015. *Public Policy and Administration*, 35(2), 201-223. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0952076718814892>
- Dolls, M., Fuest, C., Krolage, C., Neumeier, F., & Stöhlker, D. (2019). Incentivising Structural Reforms in Europe? A Blueprint for the European Commission's Reform Support Programme. *Intereconomics*, 54(1), 42-46. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10272-019-0790-7>
- Doloi, H., Sawhney, A., Iyer, K. C., & Rentala, S. (2012). Analysing factors affecting delays in Indian construction projects. *International Journal of Project Management*, 30(4), 479-489. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2011.10.004>
- Echebarria, K. (2023). Changing the World Bank's Incentives from Inputs to Outcomes. Center for Global Development. <https://www.cgdev.org/blog/changing-world-banks-incentives-inputs-outcomes>
- Ernst & Young. (2020). Executive Summary—Mid-term Evaluation of the Structural Reform Support Programme (SRSP) 2017-2020 (Framework Contract No ECFIN-001-2017 No SRSS / C2017 / 069). https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/2bdc80fc-38ac-412a-b463-38f75cfaa5e0_en?filename=mte_srsp_report_en_final.pdf
- Floricel, S., & Miller, R. (2001). Strategizing for anticipated risks and turbulence in large-scale engineering projects. *International Journal of Project Management*, 19(8), 445-455. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0263-7863\(01\)00047-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0263-7863(01)00047-3)
- Keck, M. E., & Sikkink, K. (2014). *Activists beyond Borders: Advocacy Networks in International Politics*. Cornell University Press. <https://books.google.be/books?id=JSF8AgAAQBAJ>
- Meng, X. (2015). Incentive Mechanisms and Their Impact on Project Performance. In C. Schwindt & J. Zimmermann (Eds.), *Handbook on Project Management and Scheduling Vol. 2* (pp. 1063-1078). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-05915-0_17
- Murdie, A., & Urpelainen, J. (2015). Why Pick on Us? Environmental INGOs and State Shaming as a Strategic Substitute. *Political Studies*, 63(2), 353-372. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9248.12101>

OECD. (2018). Economic Reform Programme: Monitoring Tool. OECD: Organization for Economics Cooperation and Development.

Rajala, T., Laihonen, H., & Vakkuri, J. (2018). Shifting from Output to Outcome Measurement in Public Administration-Arguments Revisited. In E. Borgonovi, E. Anessi-Pessina, & C. Bianchi (Eds.), Outcome-Based Performance Management in the Public Sector (Vol. 2, pp. 3-23). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-57018-1_1

Schimmelfennig, F., & Sedelmeier, U. (2004). Governance by conditionality: EU rule transfer to the candidate countries of Central and Eastern Europe. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 11(4), 661-679. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350176042000248089>

USAID. (2000). MONITORING THE POLICY REFORM PROCESS (14; Recent Practices In Monitoring and Evaluation TIPS). USAID. http://www.policyproject.com/policycircle/documents/advanced_tips.pdf

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